

Speeds of sound and isentropic functions of triethylene glycol monoethyl ether-n-alcohol mixtures at 298.15 K

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The speed of sound measurements have been made using a NUSONIC velocimeter based on the ring-around technique, for binary liquid mixtures of triethylene glycol monoethyl ether with methanol, ethanol, 1-propanol, 1-butanol, 1-pentanol, and 1-hexanol at 298.15 K and atmospheric pressure, across the entire composition range. Their values have been combined with those of the excess molar volumes converted to densities to give estimates of the isentropic molar quantity, κ_S , equal to $-(\delta v/\delta p)_S$, and of its excess counterpart, κ_S^E . The magnitude of κ_S^E decreases with increasing chain-length of the n-alcohol. The excess isentropic compressibilities have been compared with our previous published data with an effort to assess the effects of replacing methyl by ethyl groups and of inserting oxyethylene groups. Also, the deviations of the speeds of sound Δu have been calculated for all measured values of x_1 . The behaviour of u , Δu , and κ_S^E with composition and the number of carbon atoms in the alcohol molecule is discussed.

In our earlier paper^{1,2}, we reported the results of the excess molar volumes of triethylene glycol monoethyl ether + n-alcohol mixtures at 298.15 K. These results suggested the structural changes of triethylene glycol monoethyl ether by alcohol molecules. Since the study of ultrasonic speed and isentropic compressibility in binary liquid mixtures are of considerable importance in understanding intermolecular interactions between the component molecules, we thought it worthwhile to collect other thermodynamic quantities for these mixtures in order to improve our understanding of the molecular interactions in these mixtures from ultrasonic speed data. In the present study, measurement of speed of sound was carried out for binary mixtures of triethylene glycol monoethyl ether with methanol, ethanol, 1-propanol, 1-butanol, 1-pentanol, and 1-hexanol over the whole concentration range at 298.15 K and atmospheric pressure.

The excess molar volumes were converted to densities which were multiplied by speed of sound to estimate the isentropic compressibility κ_S for all the mixtures. Also, we have calculated the deviations Δu of the speeds of sound u from their linear dependence of ultrasonic speed.

Results and Discussion

The results of the speed of sound u as a function of mole fraction x_1 at 298.15 K and atmospheric pressure for $\{x_1\text{H}(\text{CH}_2)_2(\text{OCH}_2\text{CH}_2)_3\text{OH} + x_2\text{C}_n\text{H}_{2n+1}\text{OH}$, where $n = 1, 2, 3, 4, 5$, and 6) are listed in Table 1 and shown in Fig. 1. It can be seen that there is a monotonic decrease in the speeds of sound with an increase in the alcohol content of the mixtures. For compact and smooth representation, the experimental values of u were fitted to a polynomial,

$$u = \sum_{l=1}^n A_l x_1^{l-1} \quad (1)$$

The coefficients A_l obtained from a least-squares fit with

Fig. 1. Speeds of sound u for $[x_1\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\{\text{O}(\text{CH}_2)_2\}_3\text{OH} + x_2\text{C}_n\text{H}_{2n+1}\text{OH}]$ at 298.15 K: (O) $n = 1$, (Δ) $n = 2$, ($\square$) $n = 3$, ($\bullet$) $n = 4$, ($\diamond$) $n = 5$, ($\times$) $n = 6$ (inside box shows expanded graph at higher mole fraction)

equal weights assigned to each point are listed in Table 2 together with the standard deviations σ .

The specific adiabatic compression of solution is defined as the partial derivative of specific volume v with respect to pressure p under adiabatic condition, $\kappa_S = -(\delta v/\delta p)_S$. Then, isentropic compressibilities κ_S values can be estimated from the experimental measurements of the speed of sound u and density ρ [$= (1/v)$],

$$\kappa_S = (\rho u^2)^{-1} \quad (2)$$

Excess isentropic compressibilities κ_S^E were obtained from the relation,

$$\kappa_S^E = \kappa_S - \kappa_S^{id} \quad (3)$$

where κ_S^{id} is the isentropic compressibility for ideal mixtures of the components. This can be obtained from the expression^{3,4},

$$\kappa_S^{id} = \frac{\sum \Phi_i [k_{S,i}^* + TV_i^* (\alpha_{p,i}^*)^2 / C_{p,i}^*] - T(\sum x_i V_i^*) (\sum \Phi_i \alpha_{p,i}^*)^2 / \sum x_i C_{p,i}^*}{T(\sum x_i V_i^*) (\sum \Phi_i \alpha_{p,i}^*)^2 / \sum x_i C_{p,i}^*} \quad (4)$$

$$\text{where } \Phi_i = (x_i V_i^*) / (x_1 V_1^* + x_2 V_2^*) = x_i V_i^* / V_m^{id} \quad (5)$$

and V_i^* , $\alpha_{p,i}^*$ and $C_{p,i}^*$ are the molar volume, isobaric expansivity and molar heat capacity at constant pressure respectively, for pure component *i*. The values of $\alpha_{p,i}^*$, $C_{p,i}^*$, u^* and $\kappa_{S,i}^*$ are given in Table 3. The density values (ρ) of the mixtures at the appropriate mole fraction used in the ultrasonic speed measurements were obtained from molar volumes of pure components and the excess molar volumes reported earlier^{1,2}.

Table 1. Ultrasonic speed (*u*), deviation (Δu) from ultrasonic speed in an ideal mixture (u^{id}), isentropic compressibility (κ_S) and the corresponding excess quantity (κ_S^E) for triethylene glycol monoethyl ether + n-alcohol mixtures at 298.15 K

x_1	u m s ⁻¹	Δu m s ⁻¹	κ_S Tpa ⁻¹	κ_S^E Tpa ⁻¹	x_1	u m s ⁻¹	Δu m s ⁻¹	κ_S Tpa ⁻¹	κ_S^E Tpa ⁻¹
$x_1 C_2H_5[O(CH_2)_2]_3OH + x_2 CH_3OH$									
0.0009	1103.1	2.31	1043.70	-4.14	0.3874	1347.3	124.07	572.90	-67.50
0.0027	1106.4	5.04	1034.98	-8.57	0.4442	1360.3	119.08	556.62	-59.44
0.0044	1109.1	7.21	1027.61	-11.93	0.4948	1370.1	112.85	544.81	-52.50
0.0088	1115.8	12.51	1009.93	-19.95	0.5421	1377.7	105.50	535.69	-46.12
0.0182	1128.8	22.53	985.08	-23.53	0.5951	1385.4	96.37	526.76	-39.62
0.0264	1139.4	30.54	947.68	-43.78	0.6638	1393.7	82.91	517.21	-31.69
0.0383	1152.7	40.07	914.02	-54.01	0.7310	1400.9	68.12	509.19	-24.85
0.0558	1171.7	53.52	869.73	-66.68	0.7913	1406.3	55.12	503.23	-19.04
0.0686	1184.5	62.27	841.58	-73.59	0.8644	1411.5	37.16	497.35	-12.28
0.0835	1198.2	71.25	812.76	-79.46	0.8795	1412.3	33.17	496.34	-10.87
0.1060	1217.3	83.22	774.97	-85.77	0.8961	1413.4	29.02	495.13	-9.50
0.1285	1234.5	93.29	743.03	-89.51	0.9158	1414.4	23.77	493.94	-7.71
0.1619	1256.5	104.71	704.71	-91.00	0.9344	1415.2	18.68	492.90	-6.03
0.1995	1277.5	113.80	670.05	-90.08	0.9503	1415.9	14.34	492.02	-4.64
0.2409	1296.7	119.90	641.22	-85.41	0.9646	1416.1	10.01	491.54	-3.13
0.2952	1319.8	125.78	609.18	-80.56	0.9818	1416.7	5.17	490.74	-1.60
0.3407	1334.4	125.97	589.48	-74.14	0.9913	1417.0	2.46	490.34	-0.74
$x_1 C_2H_5[O(CH_2)_2]_3OH + x_2 C_2H_5OH$									
0.0033	1147.3	2.60	964.22	-4.10	0.4449	1340.2	74.72	585.13	-47.04
0.0111	1154.6	7.76	945.58	-11.83	0.5025	1352.4	71.17	568.53	-41.57
0.0242	1165.2	14.78	918.27	-21.47	0.5487	1361.4	67.53	556.81	-37.34
0.0441	1179.0	23.14	883.03	-31.49	0.6096	1372.4	61.87	543.04	-32.11
0.0567	1187.0	27.69	863.22	-36.26	0.6712	1381.7	54.33	531.32	-26.42
0.0722	1196.9	33.35	840.11	-41.77	0.7190	1388.1	47.65	523.70	-22.08
0.0853	1205.0	37.87	821.93	-45.80	0.7867	1397.0	38.04	513.37	-16.73
0.1007	1213.9	42.56	802.45	-49.44	0.8198	1400.6	32.58	509.15	-13.87
0.1229	1226.6	49.19	776.19	-54.23	0.8549	1404.3	26.68	504.81	-11.08
0.1605	1245.1	57.40	739.22	-58.11	0.8807	1407.3	22.63	501.56	-9.32
0.1915	1259.1	62.92	713.15	-59.61	0.9043	1409.7	18.57	498.87	-7.58
0.2402	1279.0	69.50	678.32	-59.97	0.9244	1411.4	14.78	496.83	-5.97
0.2535	1284.6	71.47	669.30	-60.35	0.9374	1412.8	12.62	495.35	-5.14
0.2858	1295.7	73.73	651.05	-58.83	0.9581	1413.7	7.86	493.94	-2.96
0.3251	1308.3	75.59	631.40	-56.50	0.9672	1415.1	5.77	493.32	-2.04
0.3755	1322.8	76.30	609.72	-52.88	0.9783	1416.2	3.83	492.17	-1.33
0.4130	1332.4	75.64	595.88	-49.71	0.9862	1417.2	2.67	491.18	-0.02
$x_1 C_2H_5[O(CH_2)_2]_3OH + x_2 C_3H_7OH$									
0.0036	1205.8	0.43	858.44	-0.55	0.4670	1346.5	42.57	582.98	-29.21
0.0059	1208.4	2.50	853.47	-3.55	0.5058	1353.2	41.02	572.92	-26.87
0.0099	1210.0	3.29	849.10	-4.52	0.5582	1362.7	39.37	559.67	-24.54
0.0175	1214.0	5.68	839.54	-7.71	0.6191	1372.3	36.02	546.47	-21.13
0.0252	1217.4	7.44	830.95	-9.98	0.6674	1379.8	33.24	536.74	-18.70
0.0364	1222.7	10.36	818.42	-13.54	0.7134	1385.9	29.56	528.67	-15.94
0.0463	1226.8	12.35	808.41	-15.82	0.7601	1392.0	25.73	520.93	-13.35
0.0554	1230.4	14.02	799.70	-17.60	0.8226	1399.4	19.83	511.61	-9.82
0.0692	1236.0	16.68	786.66	-20.43	0.8712	1405.1	15.20	504.79	-7.33
0.0877	1243.4	20.15	770.11	-23.81	0.8955	1407.8	12.73	501.56	-6.11
0.1075	1250.8	23.33	753.93	-26.52	0.9156	1409.7	10.35	499.21	-4.87
0.1641	1270.5	31.00	713.23	-31.95	0.9276	1410.9	9.00	497.77	-4.22
0.2172	1286.0	35.20	682.55	-33.30	0.9413	1412.4	7.59	496.03	-3.60
0.2682	1301.2	39.55	655.74	-34.81	0.9514	1412.8	5.84	495.26	-2.65
0.3226	1315.3	42.08	631.80	-34.42	0.9723	1415.0	3.59	492.79	-1.64
0.3802	1328.3	42.83	610.55	-32.46	0.9901	1416.7	1.50	490.79	-0.74
0.4276	1338.7	43.15	594.63	-30.99					

Table-1 (contd.)

$x_1C_2H_5(O(CH_2)_2)_3OH + x_2C_4H_9OH$									
0.0019	1240.8	0.06	806.10	-0.45	0.4311	1337.7	21.04	600.70	-19.19
0.0046	1241.3	0.09	804.06	-0.86	0.4750	1345.0	20.57	588.63	-17.89
0.0082	1242.0	0.15	801.03	-1.74	0.5228	1353.1	20.22	576.02	-16.77
0.0130	1243.2	0.50	797.61	-2.30	0.5864	1363.2	19.07	560.89	-14.83
0.0205	1245.4	1.37	791.96	-3.54	0.6357	1370.5	17.64	550.23	-13.13
0.0293	1247.8	2.22	785.64	-4.76	0.6781	1377.0	16.64	541.30	-11.97
0.0386	1250.3	3.07	779.16	-5.94	0.7566	1387.7	13.46	526.72	-9.08
0.0572	1255.2	4.68	766.74	-8.00	0.7999	1393.5	11.60	519.23	-7.55
0.0850	1262.6	7.16	748.82	-11.05	0.8533	1400.3	8.95	510.60	-5.61
0.1186	1270.7	9.31	729.47	-13.33	0.8985	1405.5	6.16	504.00	-3.71
0.1728	1284.3	13.33	700.16	-17.00	0.9288	1409.2	4.50	499.57	-2.65
0.2146	1293.7	15.33	680.52	-18.31	0.9549	1412.5	3.18	495.76	-1.86
0.2632	1303.9	16.94	659.99	-18.94	0.9673	1414.2	2.68	493.84	-1.63
0.2992	1312.2	18.87	645.00	-20.08	0.9788	1415.3	1.75	492.43	-1.08
0.3143	1314.4	18.90	640.22	-20.26	0.9872	1416.1	1.06	491.44	-0.65
0.3307	1318.5	19.60	633.51	-20.02	0.9935	1416.8	0.65	490.62	-0.41
0.3806	1328.2	20.47	616.55	-19.69					
$x_1C_2H_5(O(CH_2)_2)_3OH + x_2C_5H_{11}OH$									
0.0026	1274.5	0.32	758.26	-0.41	0.5228	1356.3	7.48	577.57	-9.86
0.0064	1275.1	0.38	756.33	-0.69	0.5868	1365.3	7.29	562.87	-9.04
0.0115	1276.1	0.65	753.67	-1.16	0.6341	1371.6	6.80	552.89	-8.12
0.0259	1278.4	0.88	746.74	-2.00	0.6848	1378.5	6.43	536.54	-7.28
0.0392	1280.6	1.17	740.38	-2.75	0.7518	1387.5	5.82	529.61	-6.16
0.0587	1284.1	1.88	731.49	-4.09	0.8195	1396.2	4.80	517.59	-4.76
0.0831	1288.7	3.18	719.49	-5.87	0.8598	1401.3	4.12	505.41	-3.91
0.1052	1292.4	3.50	709.86	-6.90	0.1273	1295.9	3.83	700.80	-7.57
0.1542	1300.2	4.23	690.08	-8.26	0.9234	1409.5	3.19	497.96	-2.79
0.2276	1312.1	5.64	662.70	-10.12	0.9389	1411.4	2.87	495.71	-2.44
0.2879	1321.2	6.09	642.74	-10.50	0.9545	1413.2	2.43	493.84	-1.97
0.3597	1331.9	6.48	621.03	-10.74	0.9724	1414.2	0.86	492.39	-0.76
0.3832	1335.8	7.01	613.89	-10.80	0.9826	1415.3	0.50	491.11	-0.48
0.4512	1345.9	7.35	595.45	-10.46	0.9922	1416.3	0.12	489.94	-0.14
$x_1C_2H_5(O(CH_2)_2)_3OH + x_2C_6H_{13}OH$									
0.0023	1301.2	-0.07	723.89	-0.05	0.5019	1356.9	-2.47	583.07	-4.27
0.0076	1301.7	-0.18	722.01	-0.20	0.5687	1364.7	-2.44	568.61	-3.83
0.0122	1302.2	-0.22	720.31	-0.40	0.6256	1371.5	-2.26	556.79	-3.46
0.0196	1303.0	-0.28	717.67	-0.64	0.6685	1376.7	-2.04	548.18	-3.18
0.0339	1304.3	-0.64	712.86	-0.85	0.7071	1381.3	-1.94	540.71	-2.84
0.0478	1305.8	-0.76	708.04	-1.25	0.7715	1389.4	-1.33	528.43	-2.51
0.0621	1307.4	-0.82	703.08	-1.71	0.8239	1395.7	-1.12	519.11	-1.93
0.0883	1310.4	-0.87	693.37	-3.00	0.8864	1403.1	-0.99	508.51	-1.12
0.1001	1311.7	-0.94	690.27	-3.30	0.9140	1406.4	-0.90	503.96	-0.77
0.1320	1315.3	-1.05	680.04	-3.46	0.9267	1408.0	-0.77	501.86	-0.64
0.1625	1318.5	-1.40	670.74	-3.82	0.9441	1410.1	-0.70	499.03	-0.44
0.2138	1324.2	-1.66	655.58	-4.40	0.9546	1411.4	-0.62	497.32	-0.33
0.2726	1330.5	-1.80	639.46	-4.47	0.9643	1412.6	-0.55	495.79	-0.20
0.3195	1336.2	-1.96	626.64	-4.97	0.9728	1413.7	-0.43	494.38	-0.16
0.3675	1341.5	-2.24	614.55	-4.86	0.9829	1415.0	-0.31	492.74	-0.08
0.4375	1348.9	-2.98	598.23	-4.61	0.9891	1417.2	-0.03	491.61	-0.06

The deviations of the measured speeds of sound from their linear dependence of the ultrasonic speed were calculated from the equation,

$$\Delta u = u - \sum x_i u_i^* \quad (6)$$

The results for Δu , κ_S , and κ_S^E are listed in Table 1. The values of κ_S^E and Δu for each mixture have been fitted to the Redlich-Kister⁵ polynomial equation,

$$Y = x_1 x_2 \sum_{i=1}^n A_i (x_1 - x_2)^{i-1} \quad (7)$$

where if $Y (= \kappa_S^E)$ is the excess isentropic compressibility, the composition is in volume fraction, and if $Y (= \Delta u)$ is the

deviation of the speeds of sound, the composition is in mole fraction. The coefficients A_i of eqn. (7), obtained by the method of least-squares, are summarized in Table 2 together with their standard deviations σ . Experimental results for κ_S^E and Δu are plotted against ϕ_1 and x_1 in Figs. 2 and 3.

For all the mixtures investigated, $\kappa_S^E < 0$ over the whole mole fraction range. The κ_S^E shows a minimum in the sequence: methanol < ethanol < 1-propanol < 1-butanol < 1-pentanol < 1-hexanol. This behaviour is qualitatively similar to that of V_m^E . Similar variation in κ_S^E occurs in the mixtures of diethylene glycol monoethyl ether⁶ or triethylene glycol monoethyl ether⁷ with alcohols. It may

Table 2. Parameters of equations (1) and (7) and standard deviations σ

Y	A_1	A_2	A_3	A_4	A_5	σ
$x_1C_2H_5\{O(CH_2)_2\}_3OH + x_2CH_3OH$						
u (m s ⁻¹)	1105.5420	1272.7940	-2460.4670	2393.1970	-896.1876	1.842
Δu (m s ⁻¹)	450.2452	-267.4158	132.9583	-159.7331	172.7518	1.218
κ_S^E (TPa ⁻¹)	-360.6035	60.2796	-46.9490			1.909
$x_1C_2H_5\{O(CH_2)_2\}_3OH + x_2C_2H_5OH$						
u (m s ⁻¹)	1146.5640	764.9490	-1070.6320	870.5947	-294.2449	0.580
Δu (m s ⁻¹)	284.5438	-131.8508	89.0195	-52.9999		0.734
κ_S^E (TPa ⁻¹)	-238.6152	33.4610	-30.9737	29.4213		0.687
$x_1C_2H_5\{O(CH_2)_2\}_3OH + xC_3H_7OH$						
u (m s ⁻¹)	1205.7010	467.1512	-501.2474	368.9928	-123.3503	0.460
Δu (m s ⁻¹)	165.1978	-56.4071	39.5202	-24.5624		0.503
κ_S^E (TPa ⁻¹)	-136.7235	18.8284	-20.7922	14.7043		0.447
$x_1C_2H_5\{O(CH_2)_2\}_3OH + x_2C_4H_9OH$						
u (m s ⁻¹)	1239.6120	280.5662	-141.9938	39.4950		0.225
Δu (m s ⁻¹)	82.2303	-20.9172	-3.2189	15.9040		0.281
κ_S^E (TPa ⁻¹)	-79.4505	6.6558	-0.9673	4.1102		0.245
$x_1C_2H_5\{O(CH_2)_2\}_3OH + x_2C_5H_{11}OH$						
u (m s ⁻¹)	1274.2010	171.3741	-26.8130	-0.8582		0.394
Δu (m s ⁻¹)	28.6469	-0.6143	13.0341	4.6323		0.303
κ_S^E (TPa ⁻¹)	-42.8033	7.4646	-10.5677	-9.5490		0.251
$x_1C_2H_5\{O(CH_2)_2\}_3OH + x_2C_6H_{13}OH$						
u (m s ⁻¹)	1300.8630	106.4521	10.6592	-0.6169		0.314
Δu (m s ⁻¹)	-9.6735	1.1180	-0.8440	-1.0715		0.204
κ_S^E (TPa ⁻¹)	-18.8254	6.0446	-2.0238	0.5785		0.193

Table 3. Observed and literature values of density (ρ^*), isobaric expansivity (α_p^*), molar isobaric heat capacity ($C_{p,m}^*$), speed of sound (u^*) and isentropic compressibility (κ_S^*) of the pure liquid components at 298.15 K

Components	$\rho^*/\text{kg m}^{-3}$		$\alpha_p^*/\text{kK}^{-1}$	$C_{p,m}^*$	$u^*/\text{m s}^{-1}$		$\kappa_S^*/\text{TPa}^{-1}$
	obs.	lit.	lit.	$\text{JK}^{-1}\text{mol}^{-1}$	obs.	lit.	
Triethyleneglycol monoethyl ether	1016.1	1017.03 ^a	0.842 ^a	389.0 ^a	1417.3	1415.98 ^a	498.94
Methanol	786.4	786.61 ^b 786.54 ^c 786.6 ^f	1.201 ^c	81.21 ^d	1100.5	1101.80 ^b 1102 ^f	1050.0
Ethanol	785.5	785.13 ^b 784.99 ^d 785.04 ^e	1.092 ^e	112.64 ^d	1143.8	1142.29 ^b	973.1
1-Propanol	799.4	799.57 ^b 799.50 ^d 799.75 ^e	1.003 ^e	144.10 ^d	1204.6	1205.17 ^b	862.1
1-Butanol	806.0	805.83 ^b 805.9 ⁱ	0.932 ^b	177.0 ^d	1239.4	1239.39 ^b	807.7
1-Pentanol	811.1	811.10 ^b 811.15 ^e	0.893 ^b	208.4 ^e	1273.8	1275.18 ^b	759.8
1-Hexanol	815.3	815.37 ^b 815.9 ^e	0.870 ^e	240.30 ⁱ	1301.0	1302.45 ^b	724.7

^aRef. 8, ^bRef. 9, ^cRef. 10, ^dRef. 13, ^eRef. 11, ^fRef. 12, ^gRef. 15, ^hRef. 14, ⁱRef. 16. ^jEstimated by group additivity.

be noted that for a given alcohol, κ_S^E decreases as the alkyl chain-length as well as polar head group of the alkoxyethanol increases. The decrease in κ_S^E is much higher with addition of further OC_2H_4 group. The behavior of Δu is similar to that of κ_S^E , but with an opposite variation with the number of carbon atoms in the alcohol. However, the behavior of κ_S^E is inconsistent with V_m^E for 1-pentanol and 1-hexanol. The behavior of the excess molar volume seems

to be consistent with a minimum value of κ_S^E and a maximum value of Δu with $n = 1, 2,$ and 3 . This is normal because Δu is generally higher for a rigid structure. Negative values of κ_S^E mean that the mixture is less compressible than the corresponding ideal mixture, suggesting that there may be strong intermolecular hydrogen bonding with the lower alcohols. As the ether is added to alcohol, thereby causing a breakdown of self-associated alkoxyethanol ag-

Fig. 2. Values of κ_S^E for $[\phi_1\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\{\text{O}(\text{CH}_2)_2\}_3\text{OH} + \phi_2\text{C}_n\text{H}_{2n+1}\text{OH}]$ at 298.15 K : (O) $n = 1$, (Δ) $n = 2$, ($\square$) $n = 3$, ($\bullet$) $n = 4$, ($\diamond$) $n = 5$, ($\times$) $n = 6$.

gregates, or both and hence contribute to a denser packing of the molecule through hydrogen bonding, the speed of sound increases and κ_S^E decreases. Although κ_S^E is negative and Δu is likewise positive from methanol to 1-pentanol, indicating that excess free volume decreases when the mixtures is created, and is higher in mixtures containing triethylene glycol monoethyl ether with the lower alcohols. The effect is, that with increasing alcohol size, interstitial accommodation becomes less important, that is, the molecules of two components can not accommodate easily. This additional rigidity is a good reason for the positive values of Δu . Hence, the negative contributions in κ_S^E come from the interaction between unlike molecules, which is the most important factor in determining its magnitude. The present results for κ_S^E and Δu support the conclusion

Fig. 3. Mixing function $\Delta u = u - \sum x_i u_i^*$ for $[x_1\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\{\text{O}(\text{CH}_2)_2\}_3\text{OH} + x_2\text{C}_n\text{H}_{2n+1}\text{OH}]$ at 298.15 K : (O) $n = 1$, (Δ) $n = 2$, ($\square$) $n = 3$, ($\bullet$) $n = 4$, ($\diamond$) $n = 5$, ($\times$) $n = 6$.

drawn from our previous studies on excess molar volume^{1,2} of these systems.

Experimental

Materials were of the same grade as those used earlier^{1,2}. They were kept in tightly sealed bottles to minimize adsorption of atmospheric moisture and CO_2 . Before the measurements, all liquids were kept over 0.4 nm molecular sieves to reduce water content, and were partially degassed under vacuum.

Density (ρ) was measured with a bicapillary pycnometer (8 cm³ capacity) and relative error in density at (298 ± 0.01) K being ≤ 0.3 kg m⁻³. The speed of sound (u) was measured at 298.15 K with a Nusonic (Mapco 6080 concentration analyser) velocimeter based on the sing-around technique¹⁷ with acoustic waves of frequency 4 MHz. The original glass sample jar supplied with the instrument was replaced with specially designed low volume cell (fabricated by the Glass Technology Unit, National Physical Laboratory, New Delhi) in which the first component of about 80 cm³ was required to cover the transducer portion of the transducer assembly. The second component was introduced by mass into the cell from a glass syringe. The cell was then dipped in a water-bath (± 0.01 K). The ultrasonic speed at a given temperature was directly obtained from the average round-trip period of the ultrasonic wave in the fixed path-length between the piezoelectric transducer and reflector. The velocimeter was calibrated by measurements of the speed of sound in water as a reference, and the relative error measured against water (1496.687 m s⁻¹ at 298.15 K)¹⁸ is estimated to be less than 0.15 m s⁻¹. The precision of the ultrasonic measurement was checked¹⁹ by investigation (cyclohexane + benzene) at 298.15 K over the entire range of composition. Further details concerning this apparatus, experimental set-up and operational procedure are given elsewhere¹⁹⁻²¹. The composition of each mixture was obtained with an accuracy of 1×10^{-4} from the measured apparent masses of the components. All apparent masses were corrected for buoyancy. Conversion to molar quantities was based on the relative atomic mass table of 1985 issued by IUPAC²².

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